

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Effervescent Tablets Using Natural Excipients: A Non-Aqueous Wet Granulation Approach

Dhanashree Nale*¹, Sunita Sanap², Yuvraj Lokhande³, Kedar Shinde⁴, Rohan Shinde⁵, Nitiksha Jadhav⁶

^{1,5,6}Shivnagar Vidya Prasarak Mandal College of Pharmacy, Malegaon Bk 413115.

²All India Shri Shivaji Memorial society's college of pharmacy, Pune.

³Government College of Pharmacy Karad.

⁴Prin. K.M. Kundnani College of Pharmacy, Cuffe parade, Mumbai - 400 005.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 08 April, 2025

Keywords:

Non-Aqueous, Wet Granulation, Evaluation of Effervescent, sodium hydrogen.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15173394

ABSTRACT

Effervescent tablets and granules are special dosage forms that contain a medicine plus an effervescent base made of citric acid, tartaric acid, and sodium hydrogen carbonate. When these substances are added to water, they react to release carbon dioxide, which causes effervescence. There are many uses for these granules in daily life. Information on the different ingredients used to make effervescent granules and tablets is provided in this review. Numerous techniques, including the wet method, dry method, fusion method, hot-melt extrusion method, and non-aqueous method, can be used to create effervescent granules. Compression, dry granulation, and wet granulation are methods for creating effervescent pills

INTRODUCTION

Effervescent tablets are special dosage forms that contain a medicine and an effervescent base made of citric acid, tartaric acid, and sodium hydrogen carbonate. When these ingredients are introduced to water, they react to release carbon dioxide, which causes effervescence. Numerous techniques, including the wet method, dry method, fusion method, hot-melt extrusion method, and

non-aqueous method, can be used to create effervescent granules. Wet problems with swallowing capsules or pills can be used to make effervescent tablets, which are simple to use. Additionally, these tablets are absorbed more quickly. Citric acid is the primary acid used. Carbonate and bicarbonate from potassium and sodium are examples of alkali sources. The purpose of effervescent tablet is the dosages are easy to take. Effervescent pills facilitate better and

*Corresponding Author: Dhanashree Nale

Address: Shivnagar Vidya Prasarak Mandal College of Pharmacy, Malegaon Bk 413115.

Email : dhanashree.nalesvpm@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

faster absorption, offer excellent compatibility, and make handling doses easier. The acid and carbonate act as a buffer to maintain the stomach's ideal pH. At 15 minutes, the absorption takes place. Uncoated pills are effervescent tablets. They are vulnerable to gastric acid. They can be consumed as liquids. Patients who have trouble swallowing can take these drugs with ease. The stomach tolerates it nicely. The production of CO₂ during an effervescent reaction enhances the penetration of active ingredients into the paracellular spaces. To stop the tablets from sticking together, lubricants are used. In order to increase the bulk of the tablet, sucrose is added as a hygroscopic substance.

Mechanism Of Effervescence:

Materials And Equipment's

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Aspirin	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg
Citric acid	108mg	108mg	108mg	108mg	108mg
Sodium Bicarbonate	369mg	369mg	369mg	369mg	369mg
Saccharine	7.5mg	7.5mg	7.5mg	7.5mg	7.5mg
Cross carmellose sodium	---	---	2.4mg	2.4mg	---
Banana Powder	---	---	2.4mg	---	2.4mg
Okra mucilage powder	---	2.4mg	---	---	2.4mg
Tartaric acid	216mg	216mg	216mg	216mg	216mg

METHODOLOGY

Non-Aqueous Wet Granulation Method

Granulation: The process of turning a powdery or solid material into grains or granules is known as

granulation. It is used in a number of technological procedures in the pharmaceutical and chemical sectors. Granulation usually entails the agglomeration of small particles into bigger granules, which are usually between 0.2 and 4.0 mm in size.

Figure 6.1: Types of wet granulation

Organic solvents are used in the non-aqueous granulation process. Certain molecules are not suitable for dry mixing because they are temperature and moisture sensitive. These medications often make up a large portion of the formulation, which is made via non-aqueous granulation with organic solvents such as dichloromethane, chloroform, and isopropyl alcohol as a binder solution. Throughout this

procedure, safety is crucial, thus all equipment must be flameproof, located in a designated location, and equipped with all necessary safety precautions.

Preparation Of Excipients-

Preparation of Okra Mucilage Powder Extraction Procedure:

Figure 1 : Preparation Of Okra Mucilage Powder

1. Purchase 250g of fresh pods of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) at the neighborhood store.
2. The gathered okra was meticulously cleaned and sliced into tiny, 5 mm pieces.
3. After that, dry the tiny okra pieces in a hot air oven set at 70°C for 30 minutes, or until their weight remained consistent.

4. Use a mortar and pestle to cool it and minimize its size.
5. The powdered okra pods were placed in an airtight container for later usage after passing through filter number 22.

There are two phases involved in mucilage extraction.

Step 1: Mucilage extraction

1. Using 500ml of distilled water, precisely weigh 10g of the obtained okra powder.
2. Next, assemble the water bath and tripod stand.
3. Following that For around four hours, heat the solution at 60°C while stirring constantly.
4. The concentrated solution has cooled in a deep refrigerator at 4°C to 6°C after leaking through muslin fabric.

Figure 2: Extraction Of Mucilage

- Step 2: Mucilage Isolation:**
1. In 250 milliliters of ethanol, the extracted gum has separated.
 2. This makes it possible to filter through muslin material.
 3. Filtered through muslin cloth and washed with ethanol.
 4. In a hot air oven, the pressed mucilage was further dried to constant weight for 15 minutes at 35–40°C.
 5. To create a fine powder of dried okra mucilage extract, hard mucilage cake was ground with a mortar and pestle.
 6. After that, it was sieved using sieve number 22.
 7. Put it away for later use.

Figure 3: Isolation Of Okra Powder

Preparation Of Banana Powder-

Figure 4: Preparation Of Banana Powder

1. Gather two to three mature, medium-sized raw banana bunches.
2. The raw banana that was collected was meticulously cleaned and dried.
3. Sliced into thin pieces after peeling.
4. In a hot air oven, dry the banana slices for one hour at 100°C. until the weight remains constant was acquired.
5. Use a mortar and pestle to cool it and minimize its size.
6. The powdered raw banana powder was kept in

an airtight container for later usage after passing through sieve number 50.

Preparation Of Effervescent Granules-

1. Determine the precise weight of each ingredient.
2. Go through sieve number 60# with every ingredient. Combine all the components and move them to a mortar.

Figure 5: Preparation of Effervescent Granules

Binder preparation:

1. 5 milliliters of ethanol. As a binder, mix in some okra mucilage powder. After thorough mixing, a binding solution is created.
2. Include the okra mucilage binding solution in a powder combination.
3. Thoroughly mix it until a wet mixture forms.
4. To get granules, the resulting mixture was sieved using sieve no. 8#.
5. In a hot air oven, granules were dried for 30 minutes at 40°C.
6. The dried granules were kept above sieve no. 20# after passing through sieve no. 14#.

7. The item came in a sachet.

Preparation Of Effervescent Tablets

Stage I: The dies are filled with powdered grains.

- Step 1: Allow the lower punch to descend to its lowest position.
- Step 2: Powder is fully poured into the die's bore.
- Step 3: To ensure excess, the lower punch is elevated to the predetermined point.
- Step 4: Level the powder by passing it beneath the blade.
- Step 5: This guarantees that the die's bore is filled with a precise the next step and the volume of the powder or granules to be used.

Stage II: The bed of powder or grains is compressed.

Step 6: Lower the upper punch into the die's bore.

Step 7: Precompression provides a first blow to the powder to eliminate extra air.

Step 8: Complete compression of the powder. Step

9: The right amount of pressure is applied.

The tenth step involves moving the upper punch upward.

Stage III: Ejection of the tablet.

Step 11: Until the next step is reached, the bottom punch starts to rise into the die raising tablet's bore.

Step 12: The foundation level with the die on top

Step 13: The tablet is passed beneath a static blade and punched aside into the take-off chute.

Step 14: The lower punch is prepared for filling by moving to its lowest position on the die.

Step 15: Complete the punching cycle again.

Evaluation & Results:

The evaluation table indicates that F5 was effectively developed.

The following are F5 batch evaluation test: -

1. Thickness: 1.33 mm
2. Hardness: 1.2 kg/cm
3. Variation in weight: pass
4. Uniformity of content: -100.23

5. Friability: less than 1%

6. Disintegration: 1 min 5 sec

7. Time of effort: 50 sec

For a number of test characteristics, including weight fluctuation, hardness, friability, thickness, and content homogeneity, the F5 batch of effervescent tablets demonstrated considerable and acceptable tablet as a limits that complied with official IP specifications.

Organoleptic properties-

Colour- White

Taste- Sour

Appearance- Smooth

Shape- Standard convex

CONCLUSION:

It was determined that the effervescent reaction of citric acid, tartaric acid, and sodium bicarbonate provides superior effervescence, and that the effervescent tablet of aspirin can be prepared for rapid analgesic, antipyretic, and anti-inflammatory effect. Complementary excipients can only be utilized for formulation development, according to our review of the literature. Compared to a single unit dosage form, the gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) and delayed release of aspirin may lead to more consistent drug absorption and lower the risk of local discomfort. The non-aqueous wet granulation process produced effervescent tablets that demonstrated satisfactory results in terms of post-formulation assessment criteria. According to the results of the entire investigation, aspirin was effectively prepared and assessed as effervescent tablets utilizing a non-aqueous granulation process in conjunction with powdered banana and okra mucilage. It appears to be a promising formulation for the safe and efficient administration of medication.

REFERENCES

1. R. B. Jadhav, D. S. Sonwane, S. J. Surana, Crypto protective effect of crude polysaccharides fraction of *Abelmoschus Esculentus* fruits in rats. *Pharmacognosy magazine*. 2008; 4(15): 130-132.
2. Jinan Al- Mousawy, Zahraa Al- Hussainy, Maryam Alaayedi. Formulation and evaluation of effervescent granules of ibuprofen. *International journal of applied pharmaceutics*. 2019; 11(6): 66-69
3. A. Salomy Monica diyya, Noel Vinay Thomas. Formulation and evaluation of metronidazole effervescent granules. *International journal of pharmaceutical science and research*. 2018; 9(6): 2525-2529.
4. Pratibha Kale. Extraction and characterization of okra mucilage in pharmaceutical aid. *International Journal of scientific development and Research*. 2020; 5(4): 189-193.
5. Biswajit Biswal, Naveen Karna, Rashimika Patel. Okra mucilage act as a potential binder for the preparation of tablet formulation. *Scholars research library*. 2014; 6(3): 31-39.
6. R.B. Saudagar. Formulation, Characterization and evaluation of mouth dissolving tablets of Lisinopril by using dehydrated banana powder as a natural polymer. *World journal of pharmaceutical research*. 2015; 4(12): 763-774.
7. Ina Ba'diaGrajang and IisWahyuningsih. Formulation of *Sechium edule* Extract Effervescent Granule with the Variation of Citric Acid, Tartrate Acid and Sodium Bicarbonate. 1st Muhammadiyah International Conference on Health and Pharmaceutical Development. 2018; 54-60.
8. .Subhashis Debnath, C. Navya Yadav, N. Nowjiya, M. Prabhavathi, A. SaiKumar, P. Sai.Krishna, M. Niranjan Babu. A Review on Natural Binders used in Pharmacy. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (AJPRes.)*. 2019; 9(1): 55-60.
9. .U.D. Chavan. Mucilage from Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) Cortex - Extraction and Cultivation Evaluation. Article in *Journal of Food Science and Technology –Mysore*. 2003.
10. Tavakoli N1, GhassemiDehkordi N1, Teimouri R1, Hamishehkar. Characterization and evaluation of okra gum as a tablet binder. *Jundishapur Journal of Natural Pharmaceutical Products*. 2008; 3(1): 33-38.
11. Kunal Pala, b.Synthesis, characterization of Okra mucilage as a potential new age therapeutic intervention MOL2NET. *International Conference Series on Multidisciplinary Sciences*. 2020; 6(1): 2624-5078.
12. Ameena K, Dilip C, Saraswathi R, Krishnan PN, Sankar C, Simi SP. Isolation of the mucilage's from *Hibiscus rosasinensis* linn. and Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* linn.) and studies of the binding effects of the mucilage's. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2010; 1:529-543.
13. . Nargis Sultana Chowdhury, Sifat Jamaly, Farhana Farjana, Nadira Begum, Elina AkherZenat. Review on Ethnomedicinal, Pharmacological, phytochemical and pharmaceutical profile of lady's finger (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) Plant. *Pharmacology & Pharmacy*. 2019; 10: 94-108.
14. Bhatia Meenakshi and SangwaiyaPrerna. Synthesis, Optimisation and Evaluation of Okra Mucilage as Mucoadhesive Polymer. *Scholars Research Library*. 2016; 8(11): 159-163.
15. Nitin Sharma1, Giriraj T Kulkarni and Anjana Sharma. Development of *Abelmoschus esculentus* (Okra)- Based Mucoadhesive Gel for Nasal Delivery Rizatriptan Benzoate. *Tropical Journal of*

- Pharmaceutical Research. 2013; 12(2): 149-153.
16. Shayeri Chatterjee, Rana Mazumdar. Novel approach of extraction and characterization of okra gum as a binder for tablet formulation. *Asian journal of pharmaceutical and clinical research*.2019; 12(1): 189-192.
 17. Habtamu FekaduGemedede, Negussie Ratta, Gulelat Desse Haki, AshagrieWoldegiorgis4 and Fekadu Beyene. Nutritional Quality and Health Benefits of Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*): A Review. *Journal of Food Processing & Technology*. 2015; 6(6): 1-6.
 18. Soma Das¹, Dr. Gouranga Nandi², Prof. (Dr.) L. K. Ghosh. Okra and its various applications in Drug Delivery, Food Technology, Health Care and Pharmacological Aspects -A Review. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research*. 2019; 11(6): 2139-2147.
 19. Made DwiWidyantari, Luh Putu Wrsiati and I. NengahKencana Putra. Characteristics of Effervescent Granules Extract of Kenikir (*Cosmos caudatus*Kunth) Leaf with Various Acid Compositions as Alternative Functional Beverage Product. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*. 2021; 10(8): 1-8.
 20. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*. 2018; 2: 1274-1276, 1642, 1706-1707.
 21. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*. 2018; 3: 3312-3313, 3207, 3157-3158.
 22. Vijayalaxmi Kamaraddi, Sharath Kumar M., Chaitra Nayaka M. K., Kulpat iHipparagi and Sarojini J. Standardization of Banana flour and Banana powder to ensure economic and nutritional security. *International conference on food technology*.2010; 2: 30-31.

HOW TO CITE: Dhanashree Nale*, Sunita Sanap, Yuvraj Lokhande, Kedar Shinde, Rohan Shinde, Nitiksha Jadhav, Formulation and Evaluation of Effervescent Tablets Using Natural Excipients: A Non-Aqueous Wet Granulation Approach, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 863-870
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15173394>

